

FATTY AND AMINO ACID COMPOSITIONS OF “ONUNU” AND “MGBAM”, TRADITIONAL DIETS OF THE IKWERRE PEOPLE OF NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

Fatty acid and amino acid compositions of “Onunu” and “Mgbam”, traditional diets of the Ikwerre people of Nigeria was evaluated. In this study, both recipes were prepared using the ordinary traditional cooking methods and subsequently analysed for fatty and amino acid composition. The fatty acid profiles in the diets were characterized by four dominant fatty acids namely: palmitic, stearic, oleic and linoleic acids. The most common saturated fatty acid in the diets was palmitic and its content in Onunu ($40.07 \pm 0.07\%$) was significantly ($P < 0.05$) higher than that of Mgbam ($13.74 \pm 1.10\%$) while linoleic acid was the most common unsaturated fatty acid and was significantly higher ($P < 0.05$) in Mgbam ($49.50 \pm 0.10\%$) compared to onunu (10.55 ± 2.80). the ratio of PUFA/SFA in Mgbam was greater than 1. The amino acid profile shows that both diets contain appreciable quantities of essential and non essential amino acids with Mgbam significantly higher ($P < 0.05$) than Onunu in all the amino acids except tyrosine where the reverse was the case. Arginine ($725.33 \pm 6.25 \text{mg/gN}$) and leucine ($700.00 \pm 8.00 \text{mg/gN}$) were found in higher concentrations than other essential amino acids in Mgbam and Onunu respectively whereas methionine was present in relatively lower levels, however, histidine and arginine content of both diets were significantly ($P < 0.05$) higher than those of other reference proteins such as hen’s egg, casein and cow’s milk. Chemical scores showed that methionine (28.57 ± 0.04) was the limiting amino acid in Onunu while valine (71.26 ± 1.00) was limiting in Mgbam. The present study have shown that both traditional diets can provide substantial amount of the tested nutrients to the normal daily diets of the Ikwerre people however Mgbam was considered more ideal.

Key words: Fatty acid, Amino acid, Traditional diets.

INTRODUCTION

When talking about food, tradition is a very large subject that can be described at different levels: within social groups, as small as a family or as a function of time scale.

Traditional foods are often related to local foods and artisan foods referring to specific ingredients, location of the production and know-how. It could be the food made by grand mothers or by the native people of that locality (Cayot, 2007). These foods consumed by different ethnic groups have been the pride of culinary traditions for centuries (Achi; 2005). These traditional foods are mainly made from crops that are cultivated and processed within or around such an ethnic group or community.

Knowledge of amino acid composition of foods is essential to calculate their chemical score, which is used to predict protein quality (Morales de leon *et al* 2005) while dietary fat continues to be a major research priority because of its association with heart disease, cancer and other chronic diseases (Dagliogu and Tasan, 2003). “Onunu” is peculiar to both the Ikwerre and Kalabari people of the Niger Delta in Nigeria and prepared mainly with white yam (*Dioscorea rotundata*) and ripe plantain (*Musa paradisiaca*) while “Mgbam” is a melon-fungus cake peculiar to only the Ikwerre people.

The production of “Onunu” and “Mgbam” is basically an indigenous traditional process that has not been subjected to any scientific investigation and also because these traditional foods have been neglected over

the years, this has begun to take its toll on the overgrowing population with fewer diets to depend on and as such, it is necessary to start exploring some of these foods, hence the need to investigate the amino and fatty acid composition of the diets and thus the role in providing food security to the people.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study of “Onunu” and “Mgbam” preparation was carried out in Isiokpo community in Ikwerre Local Government Area of Rivers State, South-South Nigeria where they are produced for home consumption.

Materials: The ingredients used in the preparation of “Onunu” and “Mgbam” were purchased from Local markets in Isiokpo, Ikwerre Local Government Area of Rivers State, South-South, Nigeria.

Preparation of “Onunu”

Some quantity of peeled yam (*D. rotundata*) and peeled ripe plantain (*Musa paradisiaca*) were cut into cubes, washed and boiled with water in a cooking pot for 20 minutes. The boiled yam and plantain were transferred to a local mortar and pounded together to a paste using a local pestle. During the process of pounding, red palm oil and a teaspoonful of iodized salt were added in aliquots to improve colour and taste respectively. A local stew was prepared by frying red palm oil in a cooking pot for 2 minutes (but not allowed to bleach) after which the pot containing the fried oil was brought down from the cooking stove without bleaching so as to retain the vitamin A content of the oil. The following ingredients were added to the fried oil in the pot on ground and mixed together: sliced onions, sliced fresh pepper, sliced fresh tomatoes, Fresh fish with salt and ground crayfish to taste. The whole mixture in the pot were transferred to the cooking stove again and allowed to fry for 5 minutes after which some quantity of water was added and allowed to boil for another three (3) minutes and the stew is ready. The stew was used to serve the already prepared “Onunu” paste to make a complete diet.

*RPO – Red palm oil

Fig. 1: Flow chart for preparation of “Onunu” with stew

Preparation of “Mgbam”

Asu’, a local fungus of *Pleurotus* specie was pounded using a local mortar and pestle for about 2 minutes after which some quantity of ground melon (*Citrullus vulgaris*) seed was added to the pounded *asu*’ powder and pounded together for another 3 minutes until the mixture turned brown, appearing to clog together and exuding some oil. Ground pepper was added to the mixture and pounded for another 2 minutes. Half (1/2) desert spoonful of iodized cooking salt was added while pounding still continued. A little quantity (2 mls) of hot water were added drop wise to the mixture to form a colloid, mixed and pounded again until oils exuded from the mixture. The colloidal mixture was moulded and cold-pressed into small balls which formed the melon cake (Mgbam).

Wrapping leaves of “Omu-edu” (*Molatus* specie – a parallel veinated leaf that resembles the palm frond) were washed with clean water and a minimum of 3 moulds were placed parallel on the leaf which was folded and tied with a string. Some quantity of water was put into a cooking pot and steamed for about 7 minutes using a cooking stove before the wrapped samples were placed one by one into the pot and allowed to cook or boil for about 25 minutes. After cooking, the contents (melon-fungus cakes or “Mgbam”) were unwrapped and are ready for consumption. It may be eaten as such or used as an ingredient for cooking soup.

Figure 2: Flowchart for the preparation of “Mgbam”

Preparation of Samples for assay

The prepared samples of “Onunu” with stew mixed homogenously and “Mgbam” were dried in an oven at 70°C for 48 hours. The dried samples were ground with a hand mill into powdered form and stored in air tight containers at 4°C until required for analyses.

Fatty Acid Analysis

Fat was extracted from the food samples by the method of Erickson and Dunkley (1964) with hexane as the extraction solvent. The fatty acids in the total liquid were esterified into methyl esters by saponification with 0.5M methanolic KOH and transesterified with 1:4 HCL/methanol. The fatty acid methyl ester was injected into a Gas chromatography to obtain the fatty acid distribution and a print out copy of the distribution was gotten from the HP (Hewlett Packard) Agilent 6890N model automated gas chromatograph (GC) equipped with a flame ionization detector (FID) and fitted with a HP-88 capillary column. Each reported result is the average value of three GC analyses. The results are offered as means \pm SD.

Amino acid analysis

Amino acid profile was determined using Spackmann *et al* (1958) with the modifications described by Onyeike *et al* (2005). The concentration of each essential amino acid in a food protein is expressed as a percentage of the content of the same essential amino acid in a reference (whole hen’s egg) protein. That is the ratio of essential amino acid in a food to that of the same amino acid in egg protein expressed as a percentage is known as the chemical score. The amino acid having the lowest chemical score is known as the limiting amino acid. Chemical score was in this study calculated by the method of Mitchell and Block (1946).

Statistical analysis

Results were presented as mean \pm standard deviation. Student’s t-test as described by Pearson and Hartley (1966) and Steel and Torris (1960) were used for test of significance between the samples.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The compositions of the saturated and unsaturated fatty acid of the diets are shown in Tables 1 and 2 respectively. The diet Mgbam showed a significant increase ($P<0.05$) in the lower molecular weight saturated fatty acids like caprylic acid ($0.46\pm 0.05\%$), capric acid ($0.46\pm 0.15\%$) and lauric acid ($6.56\pm 2.12\%$) while Onunu showed a significant increase ($P<0.05$) in some of the higher molecular weight saturated fatty acids like myristic acid ($1.16\pm 0.06\%$) and palmitic acid (40.07 ± 0.07), however stearic acid was of a higher percentage in Mgbam ($8.90\pm 2.90\%$) compared to Onunu ($4.74\pm 0.40\%$).

Table 1: Composition (%) of saturated fatty acids in Onunu and Mgbam

Fatty acid	Onunu	Mgbam
Caprylic acid (C8:0)	N.D	0.46 \pm 0.05
Capric acid (C10:0)	N.D	0.46 \pm 0.15
Lauric acid (C12:0)	0.39 \pm 0.10	6.56 \pm 2.12
Myristic acid (C14:0)	1.16 \pm 0.06	N.D
Palmitic acid (C16:0)	40.07 \pm 0.07	13.74 \pm 1.10
Stearic acid (C18:0)	4.74 \pm 0.40	8.90 \pm 2.90
Σ SFA	46.36	30.12

Values are means \pm standard deviation of triplicate determinations

N.D: Not detected

SFA: saturated fatty acid

The total saturated fatty acid (SFA) contents of Onunu and Mgbam are 46.36% and 30.12% respectively. These values were higher to those of some Iranian foods that ranged from 21.5% to 38.4% as reported by Asgary *et al* (2009). Palmitic acid was the most abundant saturated fatty acid in these diets and analysis of dietary fat cholesterol level data show that lauric, myristic and palmitic acids may each exert a specific effect on cholesterol level (Kritchevsky, 1996).

The total saturated fatty acids (SFA) and monounsaturated fatty acids (MUFA) were significantly higher in Onunu (41.36% and 41.66% respectively) while Mgbam showed a higher content of polyunsaturated fatty acids (50.04%) and total unsaturated fatty acids (69.61%). Linoleic acid was the major unsaturated fatty acid in Mgbam (49.50%) while oleic acid was the major unsaturated fatty acid in Onunu (41.50%). These values were also comparably higher to those of some Iranian foods (30.9% - 52.3%) as reported by Asgary *et al* (2009) but lower to those of some traditional Turkish foods (35.52% - 84.10%) as reported by Guler *et al* (2010) and Daglioglu and Tasan (2003). PUFA and MUFA have beneficial nutritional and health values. They contribute to a reduction in the occurrence of vascular diseases, carcinoma of the uterine cervix and immunological diseases (Tonial *et al*, 2009).

Table 2: Composition (%) of unsaturated fatty acids in Onunu and Mgbam

Fatty acid	Onunu	Mgbam
Myristoleic acid (C14:1)	0.16±0.03	2.41±1.00
Oleic acid (C18:1)	41.50±0.50	17.16±2.00
Linoleic acid (18:2)	10.55±2.80	49.50±0.10
Linolenic acid (18:3)	1.43±0.03	0.54±0.20
∑ MUFA	41.66	19.57
∑ PUFA	11.98	50.04
∑ UFA	53.64	69.61

Values are means ± standard deviation of triplicate determinations

MUFA: Monounsaturated fatty acid

PUFA: Polyunsaturated fatty acid

UFA: Unsaturated fatty acid

The PUFA/SFA ratio of Onunu and Mgbam are presented in Table 3. Onunu has a PUFA/SFA ratio of 0.25 while that of Mgbam is 1.16. Knowledge of the ratio of PUFA to SFA is essential in most nutritional studies. The British Department of Health and Social security consider PUFA/SFA values lower than 0.45 as inappropriate for human health due to their association with cardiac diseases (HMSO, UK, 1994) therefore Mgbam with PUFA/SFA ratio of 1.66 can be said to be appropriate for human health with respect to cardiac disease.

Table 3: PUFA/SFA ratio of Onunu and Mgbam

	Onunu	Mgbam
PUFA	11.98	50.04
SFA	46.36	30.12
PUFA/SFA	0.25	1.66

The essential and non-essential amino acid composition of Onunu and Mgbam compared with those of other foods are presented in Tables 4 and 5 respectively. The amino acid profile of Onunu and Mgbam shows that they contain appreciable quantities of essential and non-essential amino acids however, concentration of all the amino acids were significantly higher ($P < 0.05$) in Mgbam compared to Onunu. Mgbam in contrast to Onunu is a good source of the essential amino acids when compared with those of the

3 reference proteins (whole hen's egg, casein and cow's milk). The low value of the essential amino acids in Onunu might be due to the low crude protein content of Onunu (10.83%). The values of the amino acids in these diets were comparably high to those of some traditional foods consumed in the Arab-Gulf states as reported by Musaiger *et al* (1990) and some complimentary foods commonly used in North-Western Nigeria as reported by Anigo *et al* (2009).

Table 4: Essential amino acid composition of Onunu and Mgbam compared with those of other foods in mg/g Nitrogen

Amino acid	Onunu	Mgbam	Whole hen's egg	Casein	Cow's milk
Val	210.00±1.00	305.00±0.05	428.00	438.00	362.00
Ile	260.00±1.50	325.00±0.05	393.00	345.00	295.00
Met	60.00±1.00	180.00±2.00	210.00	178.00	157.00
Leu	550.00±2.50	700.00±8.00	551.00	607.00	596.00
Try	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND
Phe	280.00±3.00	360.00±0.00	358.00	334.00	336.00
Thr	230.00±0.50	311.00±0.01	320.00	297.00	278.00
Lys	301.00±0.01	317.00±0.05	436.00	518.00	487.00
His	188.00±0.05	263.00±0.03	152.00	186.00	167.00
Arg	410.00±1.00	725.33±6.25	381.00	239.00	205.00

Values are means ± standard deviations of triplicate determinations

ND: Not detected

The non essential amino acid profile of the diets showed that in both diets, higher values were obtained for glutamic and aspartic acids. This might be due to the additional quantities derived from asparagine and glutamine which would yield ammonia and free acids during acid hydrolysis (Umoh, 1972). This result correlated with the findings previously reported by Sauvaire *et al* (1976) and Onyeike *et al* (2005). In some cases, values of some of the non-essential amino acids were significantly higher than, in some cases significantly lower than and, in others, they did not differ significantly from those of some reference proteins such as hen's egg, casein and cow's milk as reported by FAO (1972).

Table 5: Non-essential amino acid composition of Onunu and Mgbam compared with those of some foods in mg/g Nitrogen

Amino acid	Onunu	Mgbam	Whole hen's egg	Casein	Cow's milk
Asp	686.00±0.05	860.00±2.00	601.00	455.00	481.00
Ser	190.00±0.08	261.00±0.01	478.00	385.00	362.00
Glu	861.00±0.02	1310.00±1.20	796.00	1406.00	1390.00
Pro	127.00±0.07	212.00±1.20	260.00	738.00	571.00
Gly	224.00±0.04	365.00±0.05	207.00	126.00	123.00
Ala	301.00±0.01	416.00±1.60	370.00	196.00	217.00
Cys	66.00±0.02	180.00±0.09	152.00	23.00	51.00
Tyr	306.00±0.06	274.00±0.02	260.00	337.00	297.00
Reference	Present study	Present study	FAO, 1972	FAO, 1972	FAO, 1972

Values are means ± standard deviations of triplicate determinations

Amongst the 2 diets analysed, Mgbam was found to be a good source of the sulphur-containing amino acids, cysteine and methionine which plays a role in detoxification mechanism. The growth-inhibiting effect of raw navy beans fed to rats has been attributed, in part, to a deficiency of methionine (Kakade and Evans, 1965a; Kakade and Evans, 1965b). The high contents of Lysine and threonine in these diets are of nutritional significance since these amino acids are usually limiting in most cereals and legumes (Olusanya, 2008). Another limiting amino acid, tryptophan could not be estimated due to limitations of the analytical method. This amino acid was partly hydrolyzed during acid hydrolysis and hence not determined. Both diets studied are also good sources of the essential amino acids, histidine and arginine. Onyeike *et al.*, (2005) reported that histidine and arginine are required by infants for growth. The values of lysine in both diets were significantly lower than those of the reference proteins. The problems posed by the low amounts of lysine in diets can be exacerbated by its tendency to participate in chemical reactions including the Maillard reaction with reducing sugars during high temperature food processing and prolonged storage (Young and Pellet, 1990; Noguchi and del Rosario, 1982).

The chemical scores of Onunu and Mgbam compared with those of Hen's egg as reference protein are presented in Table 6. The chemical score of Mgbam was significantly ($P < 0.05$) higher than onunu in all the amino acids except lysine where the increase was not significant ($P > 0.05$). Chemical scores also showed that in Onunu, the sulphur-containing amino acid, methionine with the lowest value of $28.57 \pm 4.04\%$ was the most or first limiting amino acid while valine (71.26 ± 1.00) was the first limiting amino acid in Mgbam.

Table 6: Chemical scores (%) of Onunu and Mgbam compared to those of Hen's egg as reference protein

Essential amino acid	Hen's egg (mg/100g)	Chemical Scores	
		Onunu	Mgbam
Val	428.00	49.00±4.06	71.26±1.00
Ile	393.00	66.15±0.15	82.09±2.69
Met	210.00	28.57±4.04	85.71±2.50
Leu	551.00	99.82±0.41	127.04±7.01
Phe	358.00	78.21±0.21	100.43±1.88
Thr	320.00	71.87±1.87	97.18±1.96
Lys	436.00	69.03±1.22	72.70±0.40
His	152.00	118.42±2.42	173.02±1.02
Arg	381.00	107.61±0.61	190.28±12.21

Values are means \pm standard deviation of triplicate determinations

The values on limiting amino acid did not support the report of Bingham (1977) that the essential amino acid most often acting in a limiting capacity is lysine. Animal proteins are first class while plant proteins are second class and, in any protein, the amino acid whose chemical score is further most below the standard level required for survival is called the limiting amino acid (Onyeike *et al.*, 2005). The chemical score is thus a grading in which the quality of a protein can be made by comparing its amino acid content with that of a reference protein, and it recognizes that the value of a protein is determined by the content of its essential amino acid (Onyeike *et al.*, 2005).

In conclusion, the present study have shown that the traditional diets, Onunu and Mgbam can provide substantial amount of fatty and amino acid to the normal daily diets of the Ikwerre people however, Mgbam was considered more ideal.

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